

Green Startup Report 2026

Foreword

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Carsten Schneider'.

Carsten Schneider

Federal Minister for the Environment, Climate Action, Nature Conservation and Nuclear Safety

The green start-up community in Germany continues to grow, generating important momentum for the modernisation of our economy. Start-ups are developing innovative ideas that make our country fit for the future: ideas that save resources, reduce greenhouse gases, and produce fossil-free energy. In these times of high tariffs, vulnerable supply chains and geopolitical conflicts, this is more important than ever.

Expanding renewable energies, for example, makes us less reliant on oil and gas imports and secures our energy supply. Solar and wind power strengthen energy security!

GreenTech has long been a key sector. According to a report by the World Economic Forum, in 2024 the green economy had a turnover of five trillion dollars, and it continues to grow. There is huge potential in this. I want to make sure Germany harnesses that potential.

For me, this includes establishing a clear and reliable framework. That is why we are consistently pursuing the goal of climate neutrality by 2045, advancing the energy transition and building a circular economy.

At the same time, it is vital to create a climate that fosters start-up and scale-up companies. We will facilitate access to the capital market and make it easier to raise equity capital. The German government has laid a solid foundation with the Germany Fund and the WIN Initiative on Growth and Innovation Capital

for Germany. Our goal is to once again make Germany an attractive business location for investors. This is how the jobs and business models of the future are created.

The Green Startup Report 2026 is a key indicator which shows us where we stand. For example, one positive finding is that women are far more likely to be in management positions in green start-ups than in other start-up businesses. Given that mixed teams have been found to be more successful, this raises the chances that a business will be profitable for the long term.

In other areas we need to take countermeasures, for example to combat the waning momentum in green start-ups or address structural shifts in the sector. We are taking these issues seriously because Germany must remain a strong location for green start-up and scale-up companies. Let us ensure that the best ideas originate in Germany, are developed here, and remain here. And let us do so in a sustainable manner and in harmony with nature and the environment! I am committed to actively working toward this goal.

Preface

Prof. Dr. Klaus Fichter
Director, Borderstep Institute for
Innovation and Sustainability gGmbH

In a world of multiple crises and fundamental upheavals, the positive news must not be overlooked: the green start-up scene has continued to grow. A community of almost 4,700 innovative young companies is developing future-oriented solutions for climate protection, resource sovereignty, and resilience with courage and visionary power, thereby strengthening Germany as a business location. However, it is also true that the number of new start-ups and the relative importance of green start-ups in the German ecosystem has declined. We show how this can be countered in the section „Conclusions and recommendations.“

The fact that the Green Startup Report’s partner network is constantly growing sends a strong message. I am delighted that we now have the opportunity to work with over 20 renowned partner organizations from the German start-up and innovation

ecosystem on the design, analysis of results, and dissemination of the report. I would like to express my sincere thanks to all our partners for this!

Building on the scientific expertise of the Borderstep Institute, the annual monitoring of the green start-up scene is now in its 13th year. We have continuously improved the coverage, analysis methodology, and explanatory power of our data while ensuring comparability over the years, so that trends and changes can be identified over long periods of time. Continuity and methodological quality are the fundamental ingredients for meaningful monitoring.

Continuity also means that we are once again integrating our „Spotlights“ section this year. We invite colleagues from the research community to present their latest findings and insights

on green start-ups and their specific challenges and potential in the Green Startup Report.

What’s new? Firstly, thanks to the register-based database we have been using since last year, we can present a reliable analysis of the absolute figures for all green start-ups under ten years old in Germany. Secondly, thanks to the collaboration of our colleague Prof. Dr. Jörn Block in the GSR team, we are able to present for the first time the patent activities of green start-ups, an important facet of the technological performance of the GreenTech scene.

We welcome your suggestions for further topics and aspects that the GSR should address in the future.

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Goals of the Green Startup Report and Definition of green start-ups

Characteristics of green start-ups

- > Start-ups are **less than 10 years old**,
- > are **(highly) innovative** and/or have **(planned) employee or revenue growth**,
- > and **contribute through their products and services** to the **environmental goals** Green Economy.

7

key facts from the GSR 2026

Green start-up community continues to grow

The absolute number of green start-ups has continued to grow. The total number of green start-ups founded in Germany over a 10-year period has risen by 6% to just under 4,700 green start-ups (recording period 2016–2025). This indicates a stable green start-up community.

Declining growth momentum

Although the overall community of green start-ups has continued to grow, their relative importance is declining. This can be seen in the proportion of green start-ups among new companies founded in 2023, 2024, and 2025. While the share of green start-ups among all newly founded start-ups is still just under 20% in 2023, it had fallen significantly to 13% by 2025.

Patents demonstrate technological strength

35% of green start-ups with investment have at least one patent. This puts them well above the European average for start-ups that are financed by investment, around 14% of which have filed a patent application. The high proportion of patents highlights the strong technological focus of green start-ups.

Green hotspots

Green start-ups are heavily concentrated in a few federal states. Berlin (19.9%), Bavaria (19.5%), and North Rhine-Westphalia (15.9%) account for more than half of all green start-ups. In terms of the share of green start-ups among all start-ups in a federal state, Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania remains the clear leader with 28%, followed by Bremen (26%).

Green unicorns at work

The validated impact data from the Borderstep Institute shows that the climate protection potential of green start-ups varies widely, from a few hundred tons of CO₂e per year to green impact unicorns that can save hundreds of thousands of tons of CO₂e annually. On average, green start-ups reduce material greenhouse gas emissions by more than 70% compared to standard products and technologies on the market.

Faster access to initial capital

Green start-ups receive their first external financing much earlier than non-green start-ups. After 30 months, more than one in three green start-ups has completed an initial financing round, compared to only about one in four non-green start-ups. This timing advantage of green start-ups underscores their attractiveness to investors.

Women more frequently in management

At 22%, the proportion of women in management positions at green start-ups founded in 2025 is significantly higher than at non-green start-ups (16%). After the start-up phase, this proportion increases further: green start-ups are much more likely than non-green start-ups to add women to their management teams, which were initially made up entirely of men.

1 GREEN START-UPS: DISTRIBUTION, CHARACTERISTICS AND FINANCING

Green start-ups demonstrate how innovation, sustainability and competitiveness can go hand in hand. Many of the companies featured in the Green Startup Report 2026 emerged from universities and research institutions and were supported by EXIST on their path to founding a business. The report highlights the strong potential of green start-ups, while also underlining the importance of reliable support when entering the market and innovation-friendly framework conditions. Both topics therefore remain at the top of our agenda!

Dr. Armgard Wippler
Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy

➔ Number of all green start-ups < 10 years

Based on the analysis of 32,911 companies founded between 2014 and 2025 and identified as start-ups by startupdetector. The absolute number of green start-ups is extrapolated to this total population based on the proportion of green start-ups among clearly classifiable companies. The resulting values are subject to an uncertainty of approximately ±5%.

The green start-up community has continued to grow

The total number of green start-ups founded in Germany over a 10-year period has risen by 6% to 4,668 green start-ups (recording period 2016–2025). This indicates a stable green start-up community.

However, this continued growth is not due to an increase in the number of new start-ups, but rather to the fact that older start-up cohorts with even fewer start-ups are falling out of the analysis and being replaced by younger cohorts with more start-ups.

Regional hotspots for green start-ups

Green start-ups are heavily concentrated in a few federal states. Berlin (19.9%), Bavaria (19.5%), and North Rhine-Westphalia (15.9%) together account for more than half of all green start-ups founded in the last ten years.

➔ Absolute number of all green start-ups < 10 years

Based on the analysis of 29,266 companies founded between 2016 and 2025 and identified as start-ups by startupdetector. The absolute number of green start-ups is extrapolated to this total population based on the proportion of green start-ups among clearly classifiable companies. The resulting values have an uncertainty of approximately ±10% to ±40%, with higher deviations occurring particularly in small sample sizes.

➔ Proportion of green start-ups in each federal state

Based on the analysis of 2,416 green and 12,051 non-green start-ups founded between 2019 and 2025.

Relative importance of green start-ups in the federal states

In terms of the proportion of green start-ups among all start-ups in a federal state, Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania remains the clear leader with 28%, followed by Bremen (26%).

Trend reversal: relative share of green start-ups declines

A look at newly founded start-ups puts the picture of sustained growth into perspective: compared to 2023, the proportion of green start-ups among all new start-ups has fallen significantly by around a third to 13%. The absolute number of green start-ups has also declined over the past two years. They fell from 375 in 2023 to 313 in 2024 and 206 in 2025.*

This trend reversal can be seen in almost all federal states, and is particularly pronounced in the start-up hotspots of Berlin and Bavaria.

A decline in the proportion of green start-ups can also be observed among start-ups with investment.

➔ Percentage of green start-ups among all start-ups founded in the respective year (2019 - 2025 in %)

Based on the analysis of 2,416 green and 12,051 non-green start-ups founded between 2019 and 2025. For methodological reasons, the proportion of green start-ups with investment for 2025 cannot be shown at this point in time.

11 *The figures given here refer to clearly classified green start-ups. See the footnote on [page 8](#).

 The causes of this trend reversal are analyzed in depth on the following pages.

ANALYSIS

Why have **the number of new green start-ups and the proportion of green start-ups declined?**

Our analysis shows that the number of newly founded green start-ups has recently declined. With the total number of start-ups increasing at the same time, this has led to a decline in the proportion of green start-ups.

To put these developments into context, we also conducted workshops and interviews with experts from the green start-up ecosystem. The results of the analysis can be found on the following pages.

ANALYSIS

Why have **the number of new green start-ups** and **the proportion of green start-ups** declined?

1.

Shifts in attention towards other key topics (e.g., AI, security) are changing start-up decisions and funding and investment logic.

” GreenTech was very much in the spotlight for a long time, but for over a year now, it has not been on everyone’s lips.

2.

Demand and market uncertainties reduce willingness to pay and market access for sustainable solutions, especially in the case of cost-intensive business models.

” The big question is: Who will ultimately pay for it? And I’m experiencing a lot of uncertainty right now.

3.

Regulatory volatility and uncertainty increase planning risks and exacerbate declines, particularly in regulated and capital-intensive industries.

” If the regulatory framework disappears or is constantly changing, this is extremely difficult for start-ups.

These factors do not act in isolation, but **reinforce each other** and have been having a **particularly pronounced effect since 2023**.

➔ Industries with declining importance

Share of the industry in all green start-ups founded in comparison

➔ Industries with growing importance

Share of the industry in all green start-ups founded in comparison

Shift in the industry structure

There are significant shifts in the distribution of green start-ups across different industries. These are particularly evident when comparing start-ups founded in 2022/2023 and 2024/2025. The decline in the share of environmental technology could indicate, among other things, greater integration of such technologies into other industries.

In e-commerce and the food sector, the share of green start-ups is declining, which could be related to increasing competitive and cost pressures and a lower willingness to pay for sustainable products.

In contrast, the energy sector is seeing an increase in the share of green start-ups, which coincides with the energy crisis and a greater political focus on the energy sector.

Trend toward digitized GreenTech business models

In particular, trading, platform, and service models are becoming less important among new companies, which indicates a shift in preferences when choosing business models.

At the same time, the proportion of SaaS models among newly founded green start-ups is rising sharply from 19% in 2022 to 33% in 2024. Non-green start-ups were already more digitally oriented in the past. The proportion of SaaS models is also increasing in this sector during the period under review, but at a significantly slower rate (from 53% in 2022/23 to 65% in 2024/25).

Green start-ups are thus visibly catching up with the digital business models established in the overall start-up scene and combining them with sustainable impact potential.

➔ Distribution of business models

across all green start-ups founded in comparison

Based on the analysis of 1,274 green start-ups (756 from 2022/2023 & 518 from 2024/2025) and 6,336 non-green start-ups (3,228 from 2022/2023 and 3,108 from 2024/2025).

➔ Percentage of start-ups with women in management

of all start-ups founded in the respective year in %

Based on the analysis of 2,286 green and 11,303 non-green start-ups founded between 2019 and 2025.

Green start-ups promote diversity

In 2025, the proportion of green start-ups with at least one woman in management is once again significantly higher than that of non-green start-ups. The previous downward trend has therefore not continued.

After founding, the proportion of women in management at green start-ups continues to increase: it is much more common for green start-ups with an initially all-male management team to subsequently add women than is the case with non-green start-ups.

The results indicate that green start-ups show openness to diverse management teams not only initially, but also as they continue to grow.

Financing green start-ups characterized by cooperation

For both green and non-green start-ups, business angels and venture capital represent the most important sources of equity capital.

However, green start-ups resort to corporate and crowd investments significantly more often than non-green start-ups and thus have a differentiated financing profile.

The greater importance of these forms of investment is consistent with the above-average propensity of green start-ups to cooperate with established companies (cf. Fichter et al. 2024) and their greater ability to mobilize support through purpose and community, especially in the case of crowd financing.

➔ Sources of financing used by green and non-green start-ups (2019–2025)

Based on the analysis of 844 green and 2,828 non-green start-ups with investment, founded between 2019 and 2025.

➔ Cumulative share of green and non-green start-ups with initial external financing

up to 30 months after founding (2020-2022)

Based on an event-time analysis (Kaplan-Meier) for the period from founding to the first publicly reported external funding (right-censored as of June 30, 2025; log-rank test $p < .001$) of 1,201 green and 5,621 non-green start-ups founded between 2020 and 2022. A detailed description of the underlying methodology and results can be found in Grothey & Neumann (2026).

Green start-ups raise initial capital more quickly

Green start-ups receive their first external financing much earlier than non-green start-ups.

After 30 months, more than one in three green start-ups has completed an initial financing round, compared to only about one in four non-green start-ups.

The time advantage green start-ups have in accessing capital underscores their attractiveness to investors (see Fichter et al. 2025, p. 14).

It remains to be seen how the pace of financing for green start-ups will develop under changing market and financing conditions.

Patents demonstrate **the strength of technological innovation** of green start-ups

More than a third of green start-ups with investment have at least one patent application or patent. This puts them well above the European average for start-ups that are financed by investment, around 14% of which have a patent application (EPO & EUIPO, 2023).

The high proportion of patents illustrates the strong technological focus of green start-ups. It underlines their special role as drivers of knowledge-intensive, research-related, and legally protected environmental innovations.

35%

of all green start-ups with investment hold patents.

Methodology:

All green start-ups that had received investment were analyzed. The analysis examined whether patents existed, in which technology fields they were filed, and how green start-ups with patents differ from those without patents. The analysis is based on patent data from LexisNexis PatentSight+ (data status: 07.01.2026).

Green start-ups as drivers of innovation in energy and mobility

The patent activities of green start-ups focus on the field of renewable energies. Batteries and technologies for generating and distributing electricity and heat in particular underscore the important role green start-ups play in developing technological solutions for the energy transition.

Green start-ups are also very active in the field of transport and logistics. Electric vehicles, bicycles, alternative drive systems, and innovative solutions for transport and logistics characterize the patent portfolio.

Source: own evaluation based on the patent families and technology classes available in LexisNexis PatentSight+ (data status: January 7, 2026)

Start-ups as **catalysts** for sustainable chemistry

With their patents, green start-ups are making a significant contribution to the transformation of the chemical sector, primarily through new materials, biochemical processes, and resource-efficient production processes.

Together with DECHEMA e.V. and the ISC3 Innovation Hub, Borderstep has examined financing and support instruments for start-ups in sustainable chemistry.

[↗ The study can be downloaded free of charge here.](#)

Building materials

Paper

Inorganic chemistry

Chemical Process Engineering

Petroleum

Organic Chemistry

Biochemistry

➔ Patents of green start-ups in the field of chemistry

“ Green start-ups in chemistry develop solutions at key points in chemistry-based value chains, which find their way into innovative products in all kinds of sectors. A strong patent base is essential for these high-tech start-ups to protect their know-how and ensure freedom to operate for their innovations.

Dr. Alexis Bazzanella,
Director ISC3 Innovation Hub

➔ **Top 10 of green start-ups by number of patents and patent citations**

■ Number of patents ■ Number of patent citations

Source: own evaluation based on patent data from LexisNexis' PatentSight+ software (data status: January 7, 2026).

Technological leaders in the green start-up scene

Patent citations received are an indicator of the scientific and technological significance of inventions.

The high citation figures thus further underscore the relevance of these innovations and their potential for follow-on innovations.

The start-ups presented here are among the leading technological players in the green start-up landscape and exemplify its innovative strength and performance.

2

CLIMATE MITIGATION POTENTIAL OF GREEN START-UPS

“

Green start-ups develop innovative, market-ready solutions that address ecological challenges while strengthening Germany as a business location for innovations. The founders demonstrate the country’s strong innovative capacity. As pioneers they have the courage to drive change. Especially in times of economic transformation, this scene proves that economic success and ecological responsibility go hand in hand.

Alexander Bonde, Secretary General of the Deutsche Bundesstiftung Umwelt

”

The methodology in brief:

- **Self-Assessment** of green start-ups with scientific support
- **Calculation of the future CO₂e reduction potential** through the start-up's products and services (no CO₂ footprinting)
- **Fair comparison** between start-up solution and reference product
- **Focus on material emission differences**, no complete comparative life cycle assessment (LCA)
- **Forecast based on sales projections** for the next five years
- **Validation:** Technical review of the impact logic, assumptions used in emissions calculations, and data sources
- **Result:** Planned climate mitigation potential of the start-up upon successful market entry

Impact Analysis: **climate mitigation potential** of green start-ups

Green start-ups generate a **double dividend**: in addition to economic added value (jobs, profits, etc.), their innovative products and services also create ecological added value – for example, through climate and nature conservation or improved resource efficiency.

While there are established metrics and measurement methods for economic performance, it has been unclear until now how big the ecological impacts and potential of green start-ups are. With the GHG & Impact Estimator from ImpactNexus, the Borderstep Institute is building a unique impact database of green start-ups.

This means that, for the first time, the specific climate mitigation potential of a larger group of green start-ups can be evaluated and the question of ecological impacts and potential can be examined.

The findings presented here are based on validated results from 65 green start-ups from Germany and other EU countries, as well as the UK, Brazil, Japan, India, and Kenya.

The climate mitigation potential depends, among other things, on the development phase, age, and planned revenue growth of the start-up. A direct comparison of the results of individual start-ups is only meaningful if the assumptions are examined closely.

Green start-ups **reduce relevant GHG emissions by over 70 %**

Green start-ups contribute to climate mitigation in various ways, for example by closing material cycles, replacing climate-damaging raw materials, or optimizing production processes. When their products and services replace conventional alternatives on the market, they make a concrete contribution to reducing greenhouse gas emissions.

Looking at the key differences along the product life cycle—i.e., those processes, energy, and material consumption in which green and conventional products differ measurably—the solutions offered by green start-ups show on average over 70% lower GHG emissions compared to the respective alternative.

The remaining 30% typically arises from raw materials that are still needed and a supply chain that has not yet been fully decarbonized.

➔ **Relevant GHG emissions***

Based on validated climate impact assessments of 69 products and services from green start-ups.

* „Relevant GHG emissions“ are those greenhouse gas emissions for which the start-up solution and the reference scenario differ significantly over the entire life cycle per functional unit.

➔ Climate mitigation potential of **sus.raw**

Status Quo:

Mixed residual grids in processing operations lead to inefficient melting processes.

Practical example: climate mitigation potential of green start-ups

sus.raw GmbH (founded in 2023) offers scrap2VALUE, a circular metal solution for small and medium-sized manufacturing companies. The full-service offering includes material supply as well as the analysis, shredding, and sorting of sheet metal scrap, thus providing high-quality, single-type secondary raw materials for smelting companies. By substituting primary metals and enabling more efficient smelting processes, they have an **average climate protection potential of 13,475 tons of CO₂e/year** if successfully scaled within the first five years.

Practical example **sus.raw GmbH**

What motivates you as a green start-up?

With our solution, we want to bring proven concepts from large-scale industry to small and medium-sized enterprises in order to combine climate protection with competitiveness.

Why is the assessment of your climate mitigation potential important to you?

It is extremely important for us to demonstrate clear added value. Any change management requires good arguments, and in addition to economic potential, it is important to us to be able to quantify and demonstrate the positive impact of our solution.

What are you going to do with the results of the evaluation?

We use the results as an argument for our solution on the market and for potential investors who are looking for impact investments.

Maximilian Wagner,
Founder and CEO
sus.raw GmbH

➔ Distribution of climate mitigation potential among green start-ups

■ Share of start-ups

■ Share of climate mitigation potential

Based on validated climate impact assessments from 65 green start-ups.

The **climate mitigation potential** of green start-ups varies greatly

The climate mitigation potential of the 65 green start-ups examined varies greatly – from a few hundred to over 100,000 tons of CO₂e per year. Despite some high percentage reductions per product unit, ([see p. 24](#)) the absolute potential also depends significantly on the expected scaling in the coming years.

The climate mitigation potential of green start-ups is heavily concentrated in a few high-impact start-ups – the green unicorns. For example, 9% of start-ups account for almost 80% of the total greenhouse gas reduction potential of green start-ups.

3

SPOTLIGHTS

Latest results from the **research community**

With the „Spotlights“ format, we invite colleagues from the research community to present their latest findings and insights on green start-ups and their specific challenges and potential in the Green Startup Report.

They bring their own data sources with them, or we provide the data from the Green Startup Report for additional analysis. This enables interested researchers to contribute their latest research findings.

In this way, we are expanding the data and knowledge base on the conditions for success of green start-ups, relevant trends, and the necessary design of start-up and innovation ecosystems. We are thus pooling the latest knowledge on the need for action for sustainable entrepreneurship and the success of the major transformation tasks ahead of us.

SPOTLIGHT HACKATHON

Shared data, shared insights

At the end of August 2025, Berlin became the meeting place for a new form of collaboration in entrepreneurship research. The first scientific hackathon on the Green Startup Report not only opened up data sets, but also new avenues for cooperation. Over two days, fifteen researchers from all over Germany jointly evaluated the data set on green start-ups provided by the Borderstep Institute and startupdetector. A selection of the exciting results is presented below.

The complete results will be published in a special edition of the journal „Der Betriebswirt“:

[🔗 Link to the journal](#)

“

In traditional research settings, everyone works in their own data silo. A hackathon flips that logic: data is shared, questions are developed together, and results are owned collectively. This does not just change the outcomes - it changes the culture of research

”

Malte Bau, Co-organisier,
Otto-von-Guericke-Universität
Magdeburg

SPOTLIGHT HACKATHON

Biodiversity solutions from green start-ups

In her hackathon contribution, Julia Frantsits (Borderstep Institute) opens up research into biodiversity start-ups. Based on the key questions of how biodiversity start-ups can be conceptualized and identified and how widespread they are in Germany, she examines a new category of start-ups. Methodologically, the study builds on the identification approach from the Green Startup Report ([see p. 47](#)) and applies it to the field of biodiversity for the first time.

On this basis, 41 biodiversity start-ups were identified, of which 26 offer biodiversity solutions as their core business and 15 pursue them as a secondary business. The low number of biodiversity-oriented start-ups identified to date shows that this **field of innovation needs more attention** in order to become visible and eligible for targeted support and funding in the future.

➔ What convinces investors on green start-up websites

Content has an impact

- ⊕ Emphasis on ecological sustainability
- ⊕ Emphasis on market potential

Language style does not have an impact

- ⊖ Uniqueness claims
- ⊖ Ego-Narrative
- ⊖ Fact-based style
- ⊖ Analytical and objective style

Based on an analysis of the narratives used on the websites of 584 green start-ups founded in Germany between 2014 and June 2025 and their connection to venture capital and business angel financing.

SPOTLIGHT HACKATHON

Storytelling of green start-ups

Investors care about the core content of the stories communicated on websites. This is shown by the study conducted by **Prof. Dr. Christian Schultz** (Technical University of Applied Sciences Wildau) on website narratives and their influence on the investment success of start-ups.

The **emphasis on impact and sustainability** as well as a **convincing market and scaling logic** are particularly decisive. The linguistic style of the presentation, on the other hand, plays no demonstrable role.

SPOTLIGHT HACKATHON

No significant financing differences between genders

In her hackathon contribution, **Nina Heiting** (Carl von Ossietzky University of Oldenburg) examines whether there is a difference in investment amounts between green and non-green start-ups and whether the gender of the management team plays a role in green start-ups. The results of the 2,150 companies analyzed show that green start-ups **do not receive lower investment amounts** on average. There are also **no significant differences between the investment amounts** of green start-ups **with and without women in the management team.**

Following on from this, **Tina Löffler** (University of Applied Sciences and Arts Northwestern Switzerland), **Lukas Schmidt** (Constructor University of Bremen), and **Prof. Dr. Petra Dickel** (University of Applied Sciences in Kiel) consider the perspective of investors. They show that nationwide, the proportion of investments in green start-ups **hardly differs at all**, even when considering the gender of the business angels.

→ Share of investments in green start-ups in all business angel investments by gender

Based on an analysis of 16,572 business angel investments made between 2020 and 2024.

“

Berlin's green start-ups are driving forces for a modern, sustainable economy. At the same time, they are paving the way for our goal of becoming climate-neutral by 2045. With almost 1,000 green start-ups, Berlin is the nationwide hotspot for sustainable business models. This is where solutions are created that make our city sustainable, have an impact beyond Berlin and create jobs. The start-ups are as diverse as Berlin itself: 28% of green start-ups have at least one woman in management. This confirms our approach: with the Berlin start-up Agenda 2022–2026, we are focusing specifically on impact and diversity as factors for economic success.

”

Franziska Giffey,
Mayor of Berlin and Senator for Economic Affairs, Energy and Public Enterprises

SPOTLIGHT BERLIN

Green start-ups in Berlin

Berlin is one of the most important start-up locations in Germany and also plays a central role for green start-ups.

Based on data from the Green Startup Report 2026, Spotlight Berlin provides an insight into the green start-up scene in the capital and assesses its role in the national context.

SPOTLIGHT BERLIN

Berlin is a hotspot for green start-ups

With **924 green start-ups*** that are less than ten years old, Berlin is home to one-fifth of all green start-ups in Germany. As a hotspot, Berlin thus plays a key role in shaping the green start-up scene nationwide.

In Berlin, too, a **significant decline in the share of green start-ups** among all Berlin-based start-ups can be observed. Compared to the all-time high of 23% in 2023, the share of green start-ups has halved to 11%, placing it below the average of the other federal states (13%).**

At the same time, the capital is **characterized by teams with above-average diversity**. 28% of green start-ups in Berlin have at least one woman on the management team, placing them well above the city's non-green start-ups as well as green start-ups in other federal states.***

➔ Percentage of start-ups with at least one woman on the management team***

SPOTLIGHT BERLIN

Green start-ups in Berlin focus on services and scaling

Green start-ups in Berlin receive venture capital significantly more often than in other federal states. This points to the strong focus of the Berlin scene on scaling-oriented growth strategies.

At the same time, green start-ups in Berlin are significantly less active in the manufacturing sector than in other federal states. Instead, SaaS and platform models

dominate, reflecting the location’s strong digital and service orientation.

At 21%, the proportion of patent-active green start-ups in Berlin is significantly lower than in the other federal states (33%), which is consistent with the lesser importance of hardware and production-related innovations.***

➔ Sources of financing used by green start-ups (2019-2025)*

➔ Business models of green start-ups (2019-2025)**

* Based on an analysis of 204 green and 716 non-green start-ups from Berlin and 637 green and 2,107 non-green start-ups from other federal states.
 ** Based on an analysis of 484 green and 2,402 non-green start-ups from Berlin and 1,920 green and 9,626 non-green start-ups from other federal states.
 *** Based on an analysis of 176 green start-ups in Berlin and 518 from other federal states that were founded between 2019 and 2025. For methodology, see [page 20](#).

SPOTLIGHT GEM

Global Entrepreneurship Monitor

The Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) is the only data source worldwide that enables a spatial and temporal comparison of start-up rates in many countries across all continents. Since 1999, data on start-up activity and attitudes toward entrepreneurship has been collected annually in over 50 countries.

In this Spotlight, Dr. Natalia Gorynia-Pfeffer presents selected results based on the representative GEM population survey from Germany.

www.gem-deutschland.de

www.gemconsortium.org

“ The results of the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) from 2025/26 show that sustainability and sustainable business practices play an important role for the majority of founders and established business owners in Germany. Sustainable business practices are particularly beneficial for the next generation of German companies that take environmental aspects into account. ”

Dr. Natalia Gorynia-Pfeffer is project manager for the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM), which is compiled annually by the RKW Competence Center in cooperation with the Johann Heinrich von Thünen Institute for Innovation and Value Creation in Rural Areas.

→ Consideration of social aspects

■ Founders

■ Established business owners

→ Consideration of environmental aspects

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Sustainability priorities change with a company's stage of development

As part of the current GEM Population Survey 2025, two groups were asked to what extent they prioritize social and environmental sustainability. These include founders between the ages of 18 and 64 who have started a business in the last three and a half years, as well as business owners who run a business that is more than three and a half years old.

Both founders and established business owners attach great strategic importance to social and environmental aspects.

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Sustainable business practices pay off – especially for founders

Sustainable business practices – defined here as taking environmental considerations into account – have positive economic effects for both founders and established business owners.

The figures also show that founders more often than established business owners achieved positive economic effects for their companies when they took environmental considerations into account.

➔ Environmental aspects among founders and established business owners in Germany, 2025

Because I take environmental aspects into account in my company, there is an increase in... (multiple answers possible)

4 | CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

→ **GreenTech as a field of action** in the German government's new start-up and scale-up strategy

The data from GSR 2026 shows long-term growth in the green start-up scene, but at the same time a decline in momentum over the last two years, with a drop in the number of new start-ups. GSR analyses and the GreenTech Atlas 2025 indicate that this cannot be explained by an overall decline in market demand: in view of climate change and resource scarcity, green start-ups are of

central importance for resource sovereignty, resilience, and security. Rather, the inhibiting factors are shifts in attention (e.g., AI, security) in politics and funding programs, as well as regulatory volatility and political uncertainty, which increase planning risks, especially in capital-intensive industries. The federal government must therefore explicitly recognize the economic and ecological rele-

vance of green start-ups in its new start-up and scale-up strategy, create reliable framework conditions, and prioritize the promotion of GreenTech innovations as a key area of action. A new “EXIST Mission” program, challenge-based funding, and sector-specific Grand Challenges alliances are suitable for this purpose.

➔ **Incorporate sustainability missions** into the EU Start-up and Scale-up Strategy

With its EU Start-up and Scale-up Strategy, the European Commission has presented an ambitious catalog of measures for 2025 that addresses key barriers to start-ups in Europe. From the perspective of green start-ups, which according to the findings of the current and previous Green Startup Reports are above average in terms of innovation, tech-

nology, and science, the planned measures are to be welcomed. However, in the current version of the EU strategy, the potential for sustainability and social impact remains untapped: the strategy is not aligned with the EU's transformation goals, is hardly supported by an ecosystem logic, and is not consistently mission- and impact-oriented. We

therefore recommend refining the implementation along sustainability missions and strategically aligning it with the green economy. Green start-ups are drivers of transformation and belong at the heart of European innovation policy.

→ **Impact monitoring as the basis** for an effective start-up policy

Impact monitoring at the level of start-ups and start-up support programs is key to effective, adaptive start-up policy and steering the transformation to a climate-neutral and resilient economy. However, funding decisions have so far dispensed with systematic and standardized impact forecasting. This

GSR shows that impact potential can be assessed in a well-founded and reliable manner. What is needed are robust, pragmatic indicators of economic and ecological potential and effects, such as market revenues, resilience contributions for third parties, and climate mitigation effects. Existing ap-

proaches to data collection have been highly patchy to date. What is needed are holistic AI-supported monitoring approaches that connect different data sources, enable aggregation at program and cluster level, and systematically record both positive and negative effects.

→ Targeted identification and scaling of **green impact unicorns**

The GSR's impact data shows that the climate protection potential of green start-ups varies widely, with less than 10% of start-ups accounting for almost 80% of the total greenhouse gas reduction potential of green start-ups. In the future, it will be important to identify green impact unicorns even faster using reliable impact forecasting approaches

and to support them more systematically in their scaling up, both with public funding and, above all, with private growth capital and impact investments. Climate forward financing approaches can play an important role here. They finance in advance the emission reductions or CO₂ removals that can be achieved in the future through clearly defined climate

mitigation measures. These approaches have not yet been tapped for start-ups. Estimates by the Borderstep Institute assume an additional financing volume of around €3 billion per year that could become accessible for green start-ups in Germany.

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RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

Data basis

A comprehensive analysis of commercial register data was carried out for the Green Startup Report 2026. It is based on a complete record of all start-ups in Germany with the legal form of a corporation (UG, GmbH, AG, etc.). This enables an objective and methodologically sound view of the green start-up scene.

The start-ups were identified by **startupdetector GmbH**, which systematically analyzes commercial register entries. A multi-stage process was used, combining algorithmic filtering with manual verification. Only companies that are registered as corporations and pursue an innovative, growth-oriented

business model were classified as start-ups.* As part of the Green Startup Report 2026, **32,911 commercial register entries of start-ups** founded between January 2014 and December 2025 were examined on this basis.

In addition, **71,920 commercial register entries on investments made in start-ups** were evaluated. This includes capital increases with external investors and the participation of various sources of financing such as venture capital and business angels. This allows reliable statements to be made about how green start-ups differ from other start-ups in terms of their financing structure.

Identification of start-ups by startupdetector

1. Analysis of all new companies listed in the commercial register.

100,000 newly founded companies per year

2. Automatic verification of whether the companies meet the criteria for a start-up.

Approximately 80% are not innovative or growth-oriented.

3. Manual re-examination of all potential start-ups.

Approximately 17% are not innovative or growth-oriented.

4. Final selection of innovative and growth-oriented start-ups.

Approximately 3% of all newly founded companies are start-ups.

* A detailed description of how startupdetector identifies start-ups can be found here: <https://www.startupdetector.de/datenbank/>

Distinction between green and non-green start-ups

Green start-ups are innovative and growth-oriented young companies whose products or services contribute to the environmental goals of a green economy.

The distinction between green and non-green start-ups is **based on the European Commission's Environmental Goods and Services Sector (EGSS) classification system**, whose keyword list has been expanded to over 400 specific terms for the purposes of this study. This list contains keywords that describe products and services in the green economy and serve as a central reference for classification.

A three-step, semi-automated process was developed to ensure valid classification.

- 1 Comparison of company data** with the EGSS keyword list to identify potentially green start-ups.
- 2 Examination of company websites** using large language models to identify indications of a primary activity in the green economy.
- 3 Manual review** of the potentially green start-ups identified in step 1 or 2 by experienced reviewers.

The result is a clear distinction between 3,518 green and 19,175 non-green start-ups founded between 2014 and 2025. For evaluations of the total population, these proportions are extrapolated to all start-ups recorded by startupdetector.

The methodology was validated through random sampling and comparisons with external data sources, including a complete manual review of 571 EXIST-funded start-ups. The results show a high degree of accuracy and reliability: less than 1% of EXIST start-ups were incorrectly not identified as green (false negatives) and less than 1% were incorrectly classified as green (false positives).

32,911 start-ups founded between 2014 and 2025

22,693 start-ups for which sufficient data is available

3,518 green start-ups that can be clearly classified as part of the green economy

~5,102 green start-ups nationwide, extrapolated to the total population

Well-founded estimation of climate mitigation potential with the GHG & Impact Estimator

The data on the climate mitigation potential of start-ups presented in this GSR 2026 was collected using the **online tool „GHG & Impact Estimator“** developed by Borderstep and Impact-Nexus and is based on the Borderstep Institute’s impact database.

Start-ups use the GHG & Impact Estimator to carry out a **scientifically supported self-assessment** and estimate the planned climate mitigation contribution of their products and services for the next five years. To this end, a **fair and transparent comparison** is made between the start-up solution and a conventional reference product.

The GHG & Impact Estimator provides a uniform calculation method with comprehensive assistance. The focus is exclusively on the **material emission-relevant differences along the product life cycle**. No complete comparative life cycle assessment (LCA) is performed, but basic LCA approaches and rules are followed. The quantified emission difference is then offset against a realistic sales forecast for the start-up, thus determining an **average annual climate protection potential** over the next five years.

This climate protection potential reflects the future achievable impact of the start-up if it successfully enters the market.

The methodology of the GHG & Impact Estimator is **based on international best practices** in future-oriented impact assessment, including the Impact Management Project and Project Frame.

The evaluations for the Green Start-up Report 2026 are based on the assessment of 69 products and services from 65 green start-ups. For all assessments, a technical validation of the impact logic, assumptions for emissions calculation, and data sources was carried out.

Specific CO₂e reduction
per product/service unit compared to the reference product

×

Planned **sales development** over the next 5 years

=

Climate mitigation potential

More information on the methodology of the GHG & Impact Estimator can be found in the [background paper](#).

Authorship

Prof. Dr. Klaus Fichter is Director of the Borderstep Institute for Innovation and Sustainability. He teaches at the Carl von Ossietzky University of Oldenburg, where he holds the professorship for Innovation Management and Sustainability (PIN). He is a member of the executive committee of the FGF Research Network Entrepreneurship, Innovation and SMEs and initiated the „Sustainable Entrepreneurship“ working group.

Dr. Thomas Neumann supports the Sustainable Entrepreneurship research area of the Borderstep Institute as a senior researcher. The start-up coach, scientist and lecturer works at the intersection between entrepreneurship theory and business practice and has already supervised over 300 start-up projects. His research focuses on the micro- and macroeconomic impact measurement of start-ups.

Prof. Dr. Yasmin Olteanu is Professor of Business Administration/Entrepreneurship at the Berliner Hochschule für Technik (BHT) and Borderstep Research Fellow. From September 2018 to February 2021, she worked as a research associate in the field of Sustainable Entrepreneurship at the Borderstep Institute. Among other things, she was responsible for the development of the Green Startup Report.

Tim Grothey is a research associate at the Borderstep Institute. As an industrial engineer, he leads projects in the field of sustainable entrepreneurship. His focus is on methods for assessing the sustainability of innovations and life cycle assessments (LCA). He is also pursuing a doctorate at Carl von Ossietzky University in Oldenburg on the topic of „Future-oriented impact measurement of start-ups.“

Prof. Dr. Jörn Block holds the Chair of Business Management at the University of Trier. He also heads the Steinbeis Transfer Center for Technology and IP Management. His current research and transfer work focuses on sustainability innovations and how these can be better recorded and made more visible with the help of patent and trademark data. He regularly publishes in leading journals on innovation and technology management.

Publisher

The Borderstep Institute for Innovation and Sustainability gGmbH researches the future and examines what is to come (innovation) and what will remain (sustainability). With our scientific work, we analyze problem solutions for a sustainable economy and develop future-oriented action strategies for companies, start-up teams, associations, funding agencies, and policymakers.

As an independent and non-profit research institution, Borderstep is active in the field of application-oriented innovation and entrepre-

neurship research and is committed to the guiding principle of sustainable development.

Our aim is to generate new problem-oriented knowledge that moves the world! We see ourselves as scientific pioneers of change and want to contribute to a green transformation of economic processes and lifestyles on the basis of excellent research. In doing so, we strengthen and support those pioneers and innovators in society who make sustainability a practical reality.

Partner network

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